

Analysis of the effect of the sampling conditions on the sub-23 nm particles emitted by a small displacement PFI and DI SI engines fueled with gasoline, ethanol and a blend.

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Abstract

The growing concerns on the emission of particles smaller than 23 nm, which are harmful to human health, lead to the necessity of introducing a regulation for these particles not yet included in the current emission standards. Considering that measurements of concentration of sub-23 nm particles are particularly sensitive to the sampling conditions, it is important to identify an effective assessment procedure.

Aim of this paper is the characterization of the effect of the sampling conditions on sub-23 nm particles, emitted by PFI (port fuel injection) and DI (direct injection) spark ignition engines fueled with gasoline, ethanol and a mixture of ethanol and gasoline (E30). The experimental activity was carried out on a 250 cm³ displacement four stroke GDI and PFI single cylinder engines. The tests were conducted at 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm full load, representative of the homologation urban driving cycle. Particle emissions were characterized in terms of mass concentration, by means of a Smokometer, and of number and size in the range of 5.6-560 nm, through the Engine Exhaust Particle Sizer (EEPS). The sampling was performed by a PMP compliant system, which permits to change the main sampling parameters. Particular attention was focused on the interval of 10-23 nm, to better characterize the effect of the sampling parameters on these particles, with the aim of determining a proper procedure for the measurement.

The results show the strong influence of sampling conditions on particle measurements, especially for the sub- 23 nm highlighting the necessity for a definition of an appropriate measurement protocol for this size fraction.

Introduction

Air pollution is a crucial problem for the effects on the environment and on human health. In the industrialized areas the greatest contribution to air pollution derives from anthropogenic activities, from the sources of industrialization processes and from emissions related to transport. The main source of pollution in urban areas is due to the internal combustion engines (i.c.e.). For this reason, in recent years the research world has focused its attention on the pollutants emitted from i.c.e. with the aim of reducing their emission in the environment.

The pollutants with the heaviest impact are nitrogen oxides and particulate matter (PM). Mainly relevant and of growing interest to

the scientific community is the problem linked to atmospheric particulate, for the high correlation between exposure to particulate and respiratory problems, correlation highlighted by numerous epidemiological studies [1, 2].

The factor of greatest importance for its effects on human health is the particle size, because it influences the penetration capacity up to the pulmonary alveoli.

The limitation on the number of particles larger than 23 nm was introduced by Euro 5b but effective for GDI only from EURO 6 [3].

Several studies [4] attest the influence of the sampling and dilution system on the measured volatile fraction of the particles. The necessity of paying particular attention to the sampling and dilution procedure of the exhaust gases led to the definition of a procedure for measuring the number of particles emitted by the engines. To achieve this goal, the Particle Measurement Program (PMP) introduced in Europe, a collaborative program aimed at developing analytical systems, thanks to which ultrafine particles could be measured to facilitate control in a regulatory framework. This program defines a procedure involving the use of a constant volume dilution system (CVS), a particle pre-classifier, a volatile particle removal unit (VPR) and a particle number concentration counter (PNC) [5].

With this procedure, the particles with a diameter of 23 nm or less, the nature of which is not completely known, are excluded. In recent years it has been necessary to lower the particle measurement limit down to 10 nm from studies conducted on the effects of particulate matter on human health, requiring a modification of the current sampling procedure to take into account the measurement of particles with a diameter of less than 23 nm, particularly influenced by the sampling condition [6].

Following the enactment of all the directives submitted by the European Union, more efforts have been dedicated to a significant reduction of particle emissions by optimizing the combustion process by increasing injection pressures, by optimizing the geometry of the combustion chamber, and by realization of multiple injections. Furthermore, the application of after-treatment systems such as catalytic converters and particulate matter traps in diesel and gasoline engines leads to a further reduction of particulate emissions both in terms of mass and number of particles [7].

An additional factor to consider for a reduction of polluting emissions is the nature of the fuel used. The need to reduce the PM emissions, combined with the problem of the non-renewability of fossil fuels,

has brought attention to alternative fuels for internal combustion engines.

Among these, ethanol is the most promising alternative fuel for spark ignition engines. It has several advantageous properties, which make it ideal for use as fuel in a spark ignition internal combustion engine: a higher octane number, which leads to an improvement in engine efficiency, a greater latent heat of vaporization, a higher laminar flame speed, higher oxygen content than gasoline, and the absence of complex organic compounds.

With the aim of determining a proper procedure for the measurement of the particles sub 23 nm, whose nature is not well understood, and for which there is no regulation that limits the number concentration of emissions, particular attention was focused on the analysis of the effect of sampling parameters on these particles.

Aim of this paper is the experimental evaluation the nature of particles by means the variation of sampling conditions, and the evaluation of the effect of fuel nature, i.e. gasoline, ethanol and a mixture of ethanol and gasoline (E30), on the emissions of particles emitted by PFI and DI spark ignition engines. The experimental activity was carried out in a 250 cm³ displacement single cylinder engine, four stroke, equipped with a GDI head; a PFI injector was located in the intake duct to carry out the indirect injection configurations. The investigation was performed at two engine operating points: 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm full load. Particle emissions have been characterized in terms of mass concentration and number and size, using the EEPS (Engine Exhaust Particle Sizer) to measure the size distribution of particulate emissions in the dimensional range of 5.6-560 nm.

Finally, in order to make a further comparison with the results obtained by the EEPS, for the identification of the number of particles was used a Condensation Particulate Counter (CPC) for the counting of particles down to 2 nm.

Sampling and dilution of the exhaust gases were conducted using a PMP compliant measurement system, which allowed two different sampling conditions, obtained by varying the temperature of the first stage of dilution and of the evaporative chamber: the sampling condition at high temperatures called "Hot Condition" and the sampling condition at low temperatures called "Cold Condition".

Experimental Apparatus and Methodology

Engine

The investigation was carried out on a 4-stroke single cylinder SI engine fueled with ethanol, gasoline and ethanol-gasoline blend. The engine was equipped with the cylinder head of a naturally aspirated GDI engine, that has four valves and a centrally located spark plug. A PFI injector was also located in the intake duct. A quartz pressure transducer was flush-mounted in the region between intake and exhaust valves. The engine was equipped with a commercial three-way catalyst. Engine specifications are listed in Table 1.

The in-cylinder pressure was measured by means of a quartz pressure transducer flush-mounted in the region between the intake and exhaust valves. The engine was fueled with Gasoline, Ethanol and a blend of 30% v/v of Ethanol in gasoline (E30). A lambda probe, integrated in the ETAS Lambda Meter LA4, allows the calculation of the oxygen concentration in the exhaust gases and the identification

of the air-fuel ratio. The injection timing, as well as the ignition timing, was controlled through the ETU multi-channel system (Engine Timing Unit).

Table 1. Engine specifications.

Cylinder Volume [cm ³]	250
Bore [mm]	72
Stroke [mm]	60
Compression Ratio	10.5:1

Emissions Measurement Systems

Simultaneously with the acquisition of the in cylinder pressure and the performance evaluation in terms of the average effective pressure indicated (IMEP) and its coefficient of variation (CoV_IMEP), the exhaust emissions were measured. Measurements of the particulate matter in the exhaust gases were performed. Particulate matter was also characterized in terms of size and number. In order to carry out these measurements, all instruments have been positioned downstream of the catalytic converter.

For the measurement of mass concentration, a smoke meter (AVL 415S) was used to measure the filter smoke number (FSN) which was converted in mass concentration through an empirical relation [8].

Particle number concentration and size were measured by means of a TSI® engine exhaust particle sizer (EEPS) in the range from 5.6 to 560 nm. For particle number measurements, the exhaust was sampled and diluted by means of the Dekati® engine exhaust diluter (DEED), a Particle Measurement Program (PMP)-compliant engine exhaust conditioning system. The dilution ratio was fixed at 1:79. A 1.5 m heated line was used for the sampling of the engine exhaust in order to avoid the condensation of the combustion water. This system allows the measurement of the solid particles defined by the PMP as particles that can survive after passing through an evaporation tube (ET) that has a wall temperature of 300–400 °C.

For a further comparison with the number of particles obtained by the EEPS, a Condensation Particulate Counter (CPC) was employed for counting particles down to 2 nm. The CPC was used to measure very small aerosol particles, following the growth of particles by condensation by a working fluid (butanol or water vapor) on the particles themselves [9].

A Nano Enhancer-CPC system was used (3777 Nano Enhancer-CPC 3772).

Based on an optical particle analysis principle, the CPC has a good precision and accuracy in the measurement of the number of particles. The results obtained showed the same trend as EEPS. The number concentration obtained from the EEPS and the CPC is shown later.

A schematic representation of the Emissions Measurement Systems is shown in figure 1:

Fig. 1. Representation of the Emissions Measurement Systems.

Methodology

For the characterization of the effect of the sampling parameters on the particulate matter particles, the temperature of the 1st dilution (TDR1) and of the evaporation chamber (TEC) in case of DEED, was changed. The temperature of the second dilution (TDR2) and the sampling temperature (TSL) have not been changed, instead. Two sampling condition were investigated for number concentration measurement (Table 2):

Table 2. Sampling conditions.

	TDR1 [°C]	TEC [°C]	TDR2 [°C]	TSL [°C]	DR [%]
COLD	50	50	Tamb	150	79:1
HOT	150	400	Tamb	150	79:1

The TDR2, as indicated by the Euro 5b / 6 standard, is set equal to the ambient temperature, so as to reduce the temperature of the exhaust gases before entering the particle counter, where the maximum operating temperature limit is 40°C.

The 50°C was chosen to examine a condition in which condensation and nucleation phenomena can be considered, whereas the value at 400°C in the evaporation chamber was chosen as it meets the conditions set by the procedure defined by the legislation.

The volatile fraction (α VOF) was estimated as the percentage difference of the actual sub-23 nm particle number measured from EEPS for Cold and Hot with respect to Cold conditions:

$$\alpha\text{VOF (\%)} = \frac{C_{\text{Cold}} - C_{\text{Hot}}}{C_{\text{Cold}}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Results and Discussion

The effect of the sampling conditions on the sub-23 nm particles emitted by small displacement PFI and DI SI engines fueled with gasoline, ethanol and a blend was analyzed. The effect of

ethanol/gasoline fueling on combustion was analyzed by means of thermodynamic analysis.

The tests were performed in steady state conditions. The selected speeds are representative of some of the operating conditions indicated in the NEDC cycle (New European Driving Cycle). The investigations were conducted at two engine operating points 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm. For direct injection, the fuel injection pressure was set at 100 bar.

The SOI (start of injection) and SOS (start of spark) values have been set to optimize combustion in terms of torque and stability. The start of fuel injection, SOI, was set to have a good air-fuel mixing and the fuel injection duration, DOI, was varied to operate in stoichiometric conditions.

The values of IMEP and coefficient of variance (CoV) were measured and reported in Tables 3a and 3b.

Table 3a. Combustion parameters for the different configurations examined: speed 2000 rpm

Engine	IMEP [bar]	CoV IMEP [%]	P _{max, hot} [bar]	P _{max, cold} [bar]	T _{exh}	
					T _{up} TWC [°C]	T _{down} TWC [°C]
GDI	8.3	2.2	45	44	315	315
EDI	8.9	1.6	46	48	585	255
E30DI	8.6	2.0	44	43	596	299
GPFI	8.9	0.6	52	54	606	309
EPFI	8.4	0.8	47	47	589	304
E30PFI	8.6	0.8	47	47	603	288

Table 3b. Combustion parameters for the different configurations examined: speed 4000 rpm.

Engine	IMEP [bar]	CoV IMEP [%]	P _{max, hot} [bar]	P _{max, cold} [bar]	T _{exh}	
					T _{up} TWC [°C]	T _{down} TWC [°C]
GDI	8.7	6.5	41	44	815	540
EDI	8.8	4.6	41	41	718	563
E30DI	8.7	6.8	40	40	825	540
GPFI	9.8	1.4	44	44	753	490
EPFI	9.6	3.0	47	46	708	410
E30PFI	9.6	1.1	46	44	720	570

For both engine speeds, the IMEP values were quite similar despite the use of different fuel injection and fuel configurations. There is an increase in the covariance of the indicated average pressure, due to the greater cyclical dispersion at higher speeds. It is interesting noting that P_{max} Hot and Cold values are similar, index of a combustion that evolves similarly.

In table 4 the gas emissions for GDI in Hot and Cold conditions are reported, the data refer to the average of several measurements.

It is possible to notice that the gas emissions show similar values: the variation is less than 5% within the error of the measure, in Hot and Cold conditions at both 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm.

Table 4. Gas emissions for GDI at 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm in Hot and Cold Condition.

	Speed [rpm]	CO [%]	CO ₂ [%]	HC [ppm]	NO _x [ppm]
Hot	2000	1.4	13.1	348	2187
	4000	1.4	14.1	60	1458
Cold	2000	1.4	13.1	348	2221
	4000	1.5	14.0	63	1564

Exhaust Particle Emissions

To better characterize the effect of the sampling conditions, the particles concentration for the different injection configurations was measured at row exhaust and the results are reported in Table 5.

Particulate emissions are strongly influenced by the operating conditions, the fuel used and the injection configurations.

For both engine speeds, DI configurations have larger particle emissions, whatever the fuel. This is due to the different evolution of combustion: in the DI configurations, the time for the evaporation of the fuel and for the mixing of Air Fuel is less and moreover the fuel impinges on the piston head and cylinder walls, remaining in liquid form and favoring the formation of soot [10] [11].

In PFI configurations, the fuel injected into the intake duct has more time for evaporation and mixing. In this case, particles are formed in small rich zone localized across the intake valves where despite the high temperature fuel does not evaporate completely and burns in a diffusive way [12].

Table 5. Particle mass concentration at 2000 and 4000 rpm for all the injection configurations in Hot and Cold sampling condition.

Engine Configuration	Speed [rpm]	PM_Hot [mg/cm ³]	PM_Cold [mg/cm ³]
GDI	2000	1.52	1.52
EDI	2000	0.26	0.23
E30DI	2000	11.5	14.5
GPF	2000	0.07	0.07
EPFI	2000	0.03	0.04
E30PFI	2000	0.02	0.01
GDI	4000	3.42	3.27
EDI	4000	0.06	0.06
E30DI	4000	0.94	1.28
GPF	4000	0.73	0.81
EPFI	4000	0.35	0.29
E30PFI	4000	0.14	0.18

Regarding the fuel effect, it is possible to identify a different behavior when ethanol is mixed and pure.

In DI, a larger emission for the E30 at 2000 rpm and GDI at 4000 rpm was observed. This difference is ascribable to the different nature of the E30: ethanol mixed with gasoline, forms azeotropes with the lighter hydrocarbons of gasoline, favoring their evaporation. The residual fuel, therefore, contains mainly heavier and very sooty hydrocarbons which burn in colder environments, extremely favorable for the formation of particulate particles [13]. This phenomenon is more evident at low engine speed due to low temperatures. The lowest emissions are observed for EDI for both engine speed, due to the lower aromatic content and the greater presence of oxygen which acts by reducing the formation of soot precursors.

Fig. 2 a. Particle number concentration in DI at 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm and in Hot (red) and Cold (blue) sampling condition. Particle smaller than 23 nm (light blue striped bar), particles larger than 23 nm (full bar).

In PFI, higher particle emissions are observed for gasoline, due to a lower propensity to evaporation of the gasoline molecules than ethanol. It is worth noting that E30PFI shows lower particle emissions both with respect to GPF and EPFI for both engine speeds. This result can be ascribed to the contribution of gasoline on combustion, resulting in a higher cylinder temperature than enhances the evaporation and then the mixing, as evinced by the higher temperature for E30PFI with respect to EPFI (Table 3).

From Table 5, it can be seen that the difference between the mass of particles measured in Hot sampling conditions and Cold sampling is negligible. This implies that in the analysis and study of the measured values in terms of the number and size particles, the differences can be ascribed to the effect of the sampling temperature. The analysis of the results shows the presence of particles smaller than 23 nm for each engine point, nevertheless the number is strictly dependent on the engine configuration.

In agreement with PM results, for both engine speeds in DI the lowest emissions in number concentration were observed for EDI. The number concentration is higher for the E30DI configuration compared to the GDI; it is worth noting that at 4000 rpm there is larger increase of particles smaller than 23 nm with respect to GDI.

For PFI configurations, in agreement with PM results, gasoline has a higher number concentration of particle smaller and larger than 23 nm, at each engine speed.

It is interesting noting that at 2000 rpm, the EDI shows a greater variation of particles with a diameter larger than 23 nm: this is due to the larger emissions of sub-23 nm particles, ascribable to the worsening of the ethanol evaporation at low temperature.

For E30 at 4000 rpm it's evident the largest volatile fraction for particles larger than 23 nm: this can be associated to the huge fuel impingement that can cause a larger presence of volatile, that condenses on existing accumulation particle rather than nucleate forming smaller particles and at the presence of azeotropes.

Fig. 2b. Particle number concentration in PFI at 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm and in Hot (red) and Cold (blue) sampling condition. Particle smaller than 23 nm striped bar, particles larger than 23 nm full bar.

To better analyze the effect of sampling and dilution conditions, the percentage ΔN was calculated as in Eq. (1); this value is used to evaluate the volatile fraction of particle emissions.

At low temperature dilution, the volatile material can condense on the existing particles. However, condensation is not the only phenomenon that could occur at low temperatures: for low concentration of particles in accumulation mode a smaller surface area is made available to the condensation phenomenon, leading to the nucleation of the volatile in sub-23 nm particles. For this reason, two classes of particle size were analyzed: however, more attention was paid to the size range 10-23 nm.

In DI the number concentrations of the particles sub-23 nm, as well as those higher of 23 nm, increase for Cold sampling. Particle is constituted by a solid matrix and volatile fraction [14]; by performing a low temperature dilution the condensation of the volatile component occurs, as well as the nucleation, resulting in an increase number of particles smaller and larger than 23 nm.

Fig. 3. ΔN of the sub-23 nm number in PFI and DI configurations for all tested fuels at 2000 and 4000 rpm.

In PFI a greater component of volatile fraction is observed for the particles smaller than 23 nm evidencing the propensity to nucleation with respect the condensation, because of the lower accumulation particle typical of this configuration with respect to DI.

It is worth of interest that among all the engine configurations, the E30 has a different behavior. The combination of the high volatile component emitted by the engine, the different nature of the mixture particles and the temperature value of 400° C in the evaporative chamber led to the negative percentage variation shown in figure 5. This result can be ascribed to the phenomenon of fragmentation occurring in the evaporation chamber where the volatile component evaporates reducing the particle size and increasing the number of particles smaller than 23 nm. Another aspect to consider is the re-nucleation of the volatile fraction [15].

Comparison of Number Concentration

To better analyze the result for E30 in PFI, the comparison between the number concentration measured by EEPS and CPC was performed in Cold and Hot Condition. In Figure 4 the number concentration measured for EEPS and CPC for E30PFI at 4000 rpm was depicted.

Fig. 4. Number concentration of the particle in the exhaust gases analyzed by the CPC and by the EEPS at 4000 rpm in Cold and Hot conditions.

The results obtained showed the same trend as EEPS confirming the hypothesis of the break-down of the particles and the re-nucleation of the volatile fraction.

Conclusions

The characterization of the effect of fuels and the effect of the sampling and dilution variables on the particles emitted by an engine SI fueled with gasoline, ethanol and a mixture of 30% v / v ethanol in gasoline has been realized. The engine speed was set at 2000 rpm and 4000 rpm. The tests were conducted paying particular attention to the sub-23 nm particles, whose nature was characterized by the analysis of sampling parameters. Exhaust emissions are defined both in terms of mass and number, through the use of appropriate measuring instruments.

The particles emitted depend on the engine configuration and the type of fuel used. The higher mass emissions are recorded for the DI condition, in particular for E30DI at 2000 rpm and for GDI at 4000 rpm.

Also in terms of number concentration, the DI condition presents the largest quantity. In particular, the particles emitted by the E30 are numerically larger than those emitted by gasoline; the same applies to the size of particle. This is due to the worsening of the evaporation of the compound heavier of gasoline.

Regarding the analysis of the effect of sampling on sub-23 nm particles, it is worth analyzing two particular sampling configurations, i.e. Hot and Cold. The GPFI configuration shows the highest variation of the sub-23 nm particle number, suggesting that in this condition a large volatile fraction is present in the particles.

Another interesting observation is relative to the E30PFI. Unlike the other engine configuration, the E30PFI has a high number

concentration in hot sampling. This can be due to the fragmentation of particles

These two last results best show how the dilution and sampling conditions influence particle measurements. The analysis of the effect of the dilution temperature and of the evaporation chamber highlighted the strong dependence of the results of measurement of particle number, in particular the sub- 23 nm, on the sampling conditions, thus highlighting the necessity for a definition of an appropriate measurement protocol for this size fraction.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

CoV	Coefficient Of Variance
CPC	Condensation Particulate Counter
CVS	Constant Volume Sampling System
DEED	Dekati Engine Exhaust Diluter
DI	Direct Injection
DOI	Duration Of Injection
DR	Dilution Ratio
E30	30%v/v of Ethanol in Gasoline
EEPS	Engine Exhaust Particle Sizer
ET	Evaporation Tube
FSN	Filter Smoke Number
GDI	Gasoline Direct Injection
GPFI	Gasoline Port Fuel Injection
IMEP	Indicated Mean Effective Pressure
NEDC	New European Driving Cycle
PFI	Port Fuel Injection
PM	Particulate Matter
PMP	Particle Measurement Program
PNC	Particle Number Concentration Counter
ROHR	Rate Of Heat Release
SOI	Start Of Injection
SOS	Start Of Spark
TDR1	Temperature Of The 1st Stage Dilution
TDR2	Temperature Of The 2nd Stage Dilution
TEC	Temperature Of Evaporation Chamber
TSL	Sampling Temperature
TWC	Three Way Catalyst
VPR	Volatile Particle Removal Unit
αVOF	Volatile Organic Fraction